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Oxidation Studies of *N*-Salicyloylflavanone Hydrazones with Selenium Dioxide

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Manuscript received 16 August 1985, revised 7 August 1987,
accepted 11 August 1987

RECENTLY, Barton *et al.*¹ reported that treatment of ketone hydrazones, oximes and semicarbazones with benzeneselenic anhydride regenerated the parent ketones. However, the corresponding aldehyde derivatives when treated similarly, yielded^{2,3} the azo and nitroso compounds. Formation of the products largely varies with the substrates, reagents and reaction conditions.

In the present investigation, we have studied the oxidation of some *N*-salicyloylflavanone hydrazones⁴ (1a-f) in acetic acid (90%, v/v) medium employing selenium dioxide, which has rarely been used as an oxidant for nitrogenous functions. This reaction afforded two major products, viz. salicylic acid (2) and flavones (3a-f) along with flavanone azines (4a-f) in comparatively poor yields. The probable reaction routes leading to the formation of different products are given in Schemes 1 and 2 and the results of the investigation are recorded in Table 1. The proposed reaction mechanism shows the following possibilities: (i) the formation of flavones is also possible by dehydrogenation of the starting materials followed by removal of nitrogen-

- a; R = R' = R'' = H
- b; R = R'' = H, R' = OCH₃
- c; R = CH₃, R' = R'' = H
- d; R = CH₃, R' = OCH₃, R'' = H
- e; R = H, R' = R'' = OCH₃
- f; R = CH₃, R' = R'' = OCH₃

ous moiety, *i.e.* without the intermediacy of flavanones, and (ii) flavanone azines may also be formed by condensation of flavanone hydrazones (first step of Scheme 1) with flavanones (Scheme 2).

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries using sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Structure of the compounds were checked by elemental analysis. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360 spectrophotometer at 60 MHz.

Oxidation of N-salicyloylflavanone hydrazone (1a): *N*-Salicyloylflavanone hydrazone (3.5 g, 0.008 mol) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and to it added a clear solution of selenium dioxide

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF *N*-SALICYLOYLFLAVANONE HYDRAZONE WITH SELENIUM DIOXIDE

Hydrazone	M.p. °C	Oxidation product*	M.p. °C	Yield %
1a	224	3a	99	18.4
		4a	256-58	10.9
1b	212	3b	157-58	20.9
		4b	254-55	8.8
1c	218	3c	120-22	19.8
		4c	242-43	12.5
1d	209	3d	170	19.5
		4d	252-53	8.7
1e	195	3e	155	22.0
		4e	256d	9.3
1f	193	3f	189	21.7
		4f	275d	11.6

*Salicylic acid (2) was isolated in all the six cases studied.

(2.2 g, 0.019 mol) in distilled water (4.0 ml), slowly with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h on a steam-bath and then cooled, and the grey selenium metal (1.2 g) separating was filtered off. The solution was diluted with

water and finally extracted with benzene. The benzene extract on tlc plate gave three spots in benzene-ethyl acetate (80 : 20) solvent system. These extracts were further washed with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (to remove the acidic part), then with water and finally dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The dried extracts after removal of benzene were treated with petroleum ether and kept in a refrigerator to provide a solid which was separated by filtration. The solid was treated with ethanol when it dissolved partially.

The alcohol-soluble part gave white crystals of flavone (1.93 g), m.p. 99–100° (lit.⁵ 99°). The identity of the flavone was (3a) further confirmed by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra (C=O, 1644 cm⁻¹) with the authentic sample of flavone. The alcohol-insoluble part gave yellow, nitrogen containing product (0.38 g) when crystallised from benzene, which was identified as flavanone azine (4a), m.p. 256–58° (Found: C, 81.5; H, 5.9; N, 6.0. C₂₀H₁₄N₂O₂ requires: C, 81.0; H, 5.4; N, 6.3%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1617 cm⁻¹ (conjugated C=O); nmr (CDCl₃) showed multiplets at δ 6.9–7.1 (CH₂ quartet), 4.6–4.8 (CH quartet) due to spin-spin interaction with each other, 2.5–3.1 (9H, Ar) and 7.5–8.3 (CH₂), 6.1–6.6 (OCH₃) (only in substituted azines). Other flavanone hydrazones (1b–f) when similarly oxidised gave similar products, viz. corresponding flavones (3b–f) and flavanone azines (4b–f) and have also been characterised by ir, nmr, m.m.p., elemental analysis and molecular weight determination (Rast).

The sodium bicarbonate washings collected from all the six reaction mixtures when neutralised with dilute HCl provided a white solid which on crystallisation from hot water gave salicylic acid (2), m.p. 156° (lit.⁶ 156°) in each case.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. B. V. Singh, Principal, for facilities, and authorities of D.R.D.E., Gwalior, for spectral data. One of the authors (A.S.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

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Synthesis and Evaluation of AChE Inhibitory Activity of 5-Substituted-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione-3-[(6*H*/bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxo-2-quinazolinyl)]hydrazones

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Manuscript received 12 August 1986, revised 10 February 1987,
accepted 7 August 1987

QUINAZOLINES have been found to exhibit marked pharmacological activity, such as CNS depressant¹, anticonvulsant², AChE^{3,4}, anti-allergic⁵ and antiviral⁶. The indole nucleus has also been known to display multifarious biological activity. Prompted by these reports, the synthesis of new compounds was undertaken in which quinazoline nucleus was incorporated with an indole nucleus through a hydrazo linkage.

The present study deals with the synthesis of 5-substituted-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione-3-[(6*H*/bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxo-2-quinazolinyl)]hydrazones.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in an electrical melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Structures of the compounds were verified by ir spectra, recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. The pmr spectra were taken on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. Purity of all the compounds was checked on silica gel G plates using iodine vapour as visualising agent.

6*H*/Bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoquinazoline-2-hydrazines (1a–f): The compounds were prepared from corresponding 6*H*/bromo-3,4-dihydro-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)-4-oxoquinazoline-